

Understanding Websites

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Abstract

Bluntly crawling for all the web-pages you can get has many disadvantages. Unfortunately, it is an approach where most existing crawl projects are stuck. Being smart during crawling and smart while processing the results is really difficult to achieve: this requires a wide variety of data which are not readily available at the moment.

To name a few quality enhancing contributions: how can you stay away from phishing sites, exclude erotic content, avoid SEO-spam networks, or keep fake news from polluting your collection? How can you crawl behave kindly for the website, so you are not locked-out by robots.txt rules? Which websites are better, compared to websites on the same subject? What are the aliases of a website, which you do not need to crawl again? How often should we visit a page, to have fresh data?

We need to know more about a website before we crawl it. We need to know more about a website to be able to present it to a non-research audience.

GOOGLE'S ADVANTAGE

The current situation is that Google has direct contact with the owners of millions of websites via their "Console" interface. This gives them a big advantage over the competition.

Part of our project, is an investigation whether Google or its competitors (like Bing), are willing to participate in sharing their contacts with website owners. Ideally, this triggers a wide cooperation.

In any case, a fully open platform will improve the quality of internet for everyone. We can get rid of robots.txt and other ad-hoc information suppliers.

BUILDING AN ALTERNATIVE

In the "Open" spectrum, fact collectors can help with pieces of the puzzle. Some players are expected to be eager to contribute to the effort. For instance, Amnesty International can be expected to maintain a list of hate speech, security organisations to publish phishing sites, media organisations to publish is list of "do not visit unless license".

This project provides an orchestration of website knowledge contributed by many sources: website owners, their ISPs, detected by crawl related intelligent processes, added by copyright holders, website users, and so forth.

Collected data is published unbiased: it is up to the user to interpret it. The use of the data is fully open: also commercial companies are allowed to use it. Preferably, they contribute to the required infra-structure, development, and maintenance.

This design must be capable to work (potentially) on the full internet scale of a few hundred million websites, hence on a distributed cluster of servers. It needs to provide

- an interactive interface for website owners: to configure optimal crawling, to see what is published about their website(s);
- an interactive interface for internet provides: to configure optimal crawling defaults, to monitor the websites they host;
- an interface for bulk uploads from fact providers: contributing knowledge. Data will expire when not maintained;
- an interface for querying for website facts, for crawlers and seach engine help, to improve quality;
- an infrastructure to "deep query" fact providers, for instance to inspect crawl failures and performance;
- an interface for website visitors to flag and view website meta-data, so they can see which links are unsave to follow, see what other people reported, or add tags; and a
- website-owner authentication facility.

Development will focus on designing a save, pluggable cluster implementation. Most effort is spend in shaping an open community. The interfaces will be created as demonstration, to be extended with sub-projects in 2022.

PRESENTATION

The presentation will convince the audience how important detailed website knowledge is to improve the required search engine quality.

The general design will be presented on a mild technical level, with some examples of applications. The algorithmic and legal challenges will be discussed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project is made possible by a generous grant from the NLnet Foundation.

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